

2º filtro de seleção

Base: ACM

Total de artigos: 22

Artigos incluídos: 12 (CI1=7, CI2=5)

Artigos excluídos: 10 (CE1=7, CE2=0, CE3=0, CE4=2, CE5=1, CE6=0)

ID	Título	Link	Resumo	CI	CE	Motivo da exclusão
002	Designing and developing an open source medical informatics module	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2382856.2382866	Lessons learned in planning and managing a development sprint to build a flexible, open source HL7 query service while successfully collaborating with diverse stakeholders and volunteers.		CE4	Revista
005	Design and Implementation of an Open Source 'Thin SIM' System for Collecting Data & Supporting Global Health Care	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3001913.3001923	Cutting edge communication technologies such as smartphones remain far from prevalent in most of the settings with the greatest need for improved health and development programs. As a result, designers of ICT4D initiatives often weigh difficult tradeoffs between the usability of smartphone applications for structured data collection versus the battery life, durability, cost and familiarity of basic phones. However, as this paper and our deployment experiences demonstrate, such tradeoffs are not always necessary. Most mobile network operators in sub-Saharan Africa offer value added services via simple, menu-driven applications that run directly from the SIM card. While conventional SIM applications can only be accessed by mobile network operators, this paper describes the design and implementation of a 'thin SIM' approach that does not require mobile network operator involvement. We have implemented this tool with more than 3,000 health workers and describe particular deployment experiences in Kenya, Benin, Nepal and Guatemala. We then reflect on a number of important limitations of the thin SIM approach, and opportunities for further development and deployment. Ultimately, we argue that there is an important role for SIM applications as one part of a configurable data collection toolkit for supporting global health and development programs.	CI2		
006	An open source cloud based platform for elderly health monitoring and fall detection	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3051488.3051513	The aim of this paper is to design and implement an open source e-health monitoring and fall detection system to monitor senior patients. The architecture of the system is based on a set of medical sensors and a microcontroller that communicates with a cloud. The sensors' data are collected and processed using a microcontroller, then, the data will be stored on a cloud to form a permanent record, as well as, to facilitate the diagnosis and the real-time monitoring for doctors, which plays a vital role in the patients' rehabilitation and healing process. To fulfill this, a web interface is created that gives doctors the authority to access all patients' medical records and monitor their health statuses. Furthermore, to detect whether the patient will suffer from unpredicted fall, a fall detection system is also considered. The system is composed of a microcontroller, voice recognition module, accelerometer and a gyroscope. By utilizing the information gathered from the previous sensors, a fall can be detected and an alert message can be sent to the medical personnel for immediate help and assistance.	CI1		

011	Patient health portal: a calendar paradigm	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2316936.2316944	In this paper, we propose a conceptual model of a patient health portal based on a calendar paradigm. The study begins with a literature review on health portals and their stakeholders. Then, to support the proposed concept, we made an analysis of the state of the art in health portals and their main features. We propose a conceptual model for a user centered health portal and its needs. We also make an implementation of the conceptual model in an open source content management system (Drupal). Our study does also include the preliminary results of a survey to a group of key users.	C11		
012	Demo of the medical device dongle: an open-source standards-based platform for interoperable medical device connectivity	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2077546.2077565	Emerging medical applications require networked coordination between medical devices. However, most of the medical devices in use today do not support wireless communication or network connectivity. Currently, hospitals interested in coordinated medical care would have replace existing devices with expensive new devices. We believe that existing medical devices can be extended to support interoperable network connectivity. We demonstrate the Medical Device Dongle (MDD), an open-source platform that enables such extensions to current medical devices. The MDD can attach to any device that has a data output interface (RS-232 or USB) and enables it to connect wirelessly and in an interoperable manner for various applications. We show how multiple medical devices, including pulse oximeters and infusion pumps, can be connected and controlled together using an open-source platform, standards-based connectivity protocols, and model-driven software. The demo setup consists of medical devices attached to an MDD Agent, an MDD Manager device, and a mobile phone running monitoring applications. The MDD components can communicate over Bluetooth, WiFi and Ethernet.		CE4	Resume
013	The medical device dongle: an open-source standards-based platform for interoperable medical device connectivity	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2110363.2110438	Emerging medical applications require device coordination, increasing the need to connect devices in an interoperable manner. However, many of the existing health devices in use were not originally developed for network connectivity and those devices with networking capabilities either use proprietary protocols or implementations of standard protocols that are unavailable to the end user. The first set of devices are unsuitable for device coordination applications and the second set are unsuitable for research in medical device interoperability. We propose the Medical Device Dongle (MDD), a low-cost, open-source platform that addresses both issues.	C11		
015	Implementation of SMART on FHIR in Developing Countries Through SFPBRF	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3301879.3301881	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) is an International health standard for health data developed by Health Level Seven -- (HL7) an international organization for the development of health data standards. FHIR enables data interoperability as it is based on lightweight open source RESTful services. Many developed countries which already running electronic health record systems are now focused on the adoption of FHIR to unlock its potential benefits by integrating other technologies like Substitutable Medical Applications, Reusable Technology (SMART) platform. In most of the developing countries electronic health record system does not exist because they lag in resources to invest in electronic health record systems and they are still operating on paper-based health record system, so they are unable to adopt FHIR and other related technologies like SMART. Due to which, interoperability is not enabled on this paper-based data. These countries remain at a distance from the benefits of FHIR and SMART platform to provide better patient care to their patients, quick and efficient clinical decision making and better diagnostics. This paper presents the	C11		

			implementation of SMART on FHIR in healthcare organizations of developing countries through a proposed framework SFPBRF which not only maps paper-based health record system's data to HL7's FHIR standard but also integrate the complete SMART on FHIR platform to run SMART apps on this FHIR conformed data. This paper presents successful translation (done by translation engine) of paper-based data to HL7 FHIR standard. It also shows the running of open source and internally developed SMART apps on this FHIR conformed data. Thus, by the successful mapping and implementation of SMART on FHIR through proposed framework SFPBRF we can conclude that FHIR can be adopted in healthcare organizations of developing countries and SMART on FHIR can help a lot in achieving better patient care, quick and efficient decision making and better diagnostics in developing countries.			
017	Towards a test and validation framework for closed-loop physiology management systems for critical and perioperative care	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3357495.3357499	Many of medical devices come equipped with a communication interface. Over the years, there has been interest in leveraging these interfaces to add computers to the loop to aid in decision making and automatic application of interventions. Such systems, which we call Closed-Loop Assistants (CLAs), are intended to help clinicians manage the cognitive load that can arise as the complexity of patient management increases. We present an open-source framework for examining CLA-patient interactions through software simulations of the CLA with <i>in-silico</i> patients to enable early testing and validation of proposed physiology management strategies. We show how this framework can be used to test different strategies across a small patient population. Considering a patient population is important because inter-patient variability is one of the critical factors that can hamper the ability of a medical cyber-physical system like the CLA to meet its goals. The ability to explore this variability early in the design process therefore helps us in increasing robustness of the system.	CI1		
021	The SMS-text adherence support (StAR) study: hardware and software infrastructure	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2517899.2517931	This paper details the hardware and software infrastructure used to collect data and deliver a novel intervention in an on-going individually randomised three-arm parallel group trial in a resource-limited setting. The SMS-text Adherence support trial (StAR) tests the efficacy of a behavioural intervention delivered by SMS-text to support hypertension treatment adherence compared to usual care. The intervention is a structured program of clinic appointment and medication pick-up reminders, medication adherence support and hypertension-related education delivered remotely using an automated system of semi-tailored informational or interactive SMS-text messages delivered to the 1372 recruited participants. The technical infrastructure includes mobile device-based electronic data collection at the point of care with secure remote upload of the data; the intervention delivery system; real-time query identification for screening, enrolment and participant management procedures; and monitoring and evaluation of trial processes. We are using several open-source software platforms in conjunction with off-the-shelf hardware to set-up and run a randomised clinical trial of a novel intervention in a low-resource setting.	CI2		
027	Febri: a freely available record linkage system with a graphical	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1385089.1385094	Record or data linkage is an important enabling technology in the health sector, as linked data is a cost-effective resource that can help to improve research into health policies, detect adverse drug reactions, reduce costs, and uncover fraud within the health system. Significant advances, mostly originating from data mining and machine learning, have been made in recent years in many areas of record linkage techniques. Most of these new methods are not yet implemented in current record linkage systems, or are hidden within 'black box' commercial software. This makes it difficult for users to	CI1		

	user interface		learn about new record linkage techniques, as well as to compare existing linkage techniques with new ones. What is required are flexible tools that enable users to experiment with new record linkage techniques at low costs. This paper describes the <i>Febri</i> (Freely Extensible Biomedical Record Linkage) system, which is available under an open source software licence. It contains many recently developed advanced techniques for data cleaning and standardisation, indexing (blocking), field comparison, and record pair classification, and encapsulates them into a graphical user interface. <i>Febri</i> can be seen as a training tool suitable for users to learn and experiment with both traditional and new record linkage techniques, as well as for practitioners to conduct linkages with data sets containing up to several hundred thousand records.			
028	Personal MobileCoach: tailoring behavioral interventions to the needs of individual participants	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2968219.2972713	MobileCoach, an open source behavioral intervention platform, has been developed to provide health professionals with an authoring tool to design evidence-based, scalable and low-cost digital health interventions (DHI). Its potential meets the lack in resources and capacity of health care systems to provide DHI for the treatment of noncommunicable diseases. In the current work, we introduce the first personalization approach for MobileCoach with the purpose of identifying the needs of participants, tailoring the treatment and, as a consequence, enhancing the capability of MobileCoach-based DHIs. The personalization approach is then exemplified by a very first prototype of a DHI for people with asthma that is able to detect coughing by just using a smartphone's microphone. First empirical results with five healthy subjects and 80 coughs indicate its technical feasibility as the detection accuracy yielded 83.3%. Future work will focus on the integration of personalized sensing and supporting applications for MobileCoach.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema. Apresenta uma proposta de expansão em um sistema descrito em outro trabalho.
033	Human Data Model: Improving Programmability of Health and Well-Being Data for Enhanced Perception and Interaction	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3402524	Today, an increasing number of systems produce, process, and store personal and intimate data. Such data has plenty of potential for entirely new types of software applications, as well as for improving old applications, particularly in the domain of smart healthcare. However, utilizing this data, especially when it is continuously generated by sensors and other devices, with the current approaches is complex—data is often using proprietary formats and storage, and mixing and matching data of different origin is not easy. Furthermore, many of the systems are such that they should stimulate interactions with humans, which further complicates the systems. In this article, we introduce the Human Data Model—a new tool and a programming model for programmers and end users with scripting skills that help combine data from various sources, perform computations, and develop and schedule computer-human interactions. Written in JavaScript, the software implementing the model can be run on almost any computer either inside the browser or using Node.js. Its source code can be freely downloaded from GitHub, and the implementation can be used with the existing IoT platforms. As a whole, the work is inspired by several interviews with professionals, and an online survey among healthcare and education professionals, where the results show that the interviewed subjects almost entirely lack ideas on how to benefit the ever-increasing amount of data measured of the humans. We believe that this is because of the missing support for programming models for accessing and handling the data, which can be satisfied with the Human Data Model.	C12		
041	3D technologies and the new	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2536146.2536187	3D technologies are ubiquitous in all domains of science and technology, ranging from the most simple product development, optimization and production to the more complex like aerospace industry. In a wide definition 3D technologies can be classified into virtual and physical. The virtual ones can provide computational		CE5	Revisão da literatura

	digital ecosystem: a Brazilian experience		models for many types of representation, simulation, optimization and scientific visualization. The physical 3D technologies are responsible to realize virtual models into real objects. When using a layer-by-layer deposition of material to build objects it is known as 3D printing or more technically additive manufacturing. This article presents an overview of the 3D technologies and the new paradigm for open hardware and software as well design exchange as a new digital ecosystem that will strongly impact economy the next decades. It is also discussed three strategic programs and a community for medical imaging based on free software developed at CTI.			
055	Simulation of ISO/IEEE 11073 Personal Health Devices in WBANs	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3345768.3355939	Simulating new protocols for e-health systems is very important, as it allows an initial evaluation before a real implementation is made. On the other hand, network simulators do not offer proper support to represent medical applications or components to facilitate running simulations modeling e-health applications. The lack of simulators that specify the sensor type and its communication requirements make real experiments harder. Aiming at fulfilling this gap, this paper proposes the use of ISO/IEEE 11073 standard for Personal Health Devices (X73-PHD) in e-health network simulations, representing realistic medical applications and investigating the behavior of medical devices (sensors or actuators) in Wireless Body Area Network (WBAN) scenarios. We developed a free and open-source implementation of X73-PHD for Castalia Simulator, providing five different PHD types to act like real ISO/IEEE 11073 devices in WBAN simulations. Our implementation supports Agent-initiated mode, where PHDs take the initiative to send measurements to the hub. Our implementation also supports the unconfirmed communication mode and the confirmed communication mode, where the receiver sends an acknowledgment to the sender every time it receives a packet. Simulation results showed that the confirmed communication mode did not perform well in WBANs when the interval between transmissions is too small, due to the long period of timeout proposed in the X73-PHD standard. Therefore, we propose a new extension to the confirmed mode standard that decreases the overhead of control packets over the network, using smaller timeouts and delivering more packets.	CI2		
060	Measuring Global Disease with Wikipedia: Success, Failure, and a Research Agenda	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/2998181.2998183	Effective disease monitoring provides a foundation for effective public health systems. This has historically been accomplished with patient contact and bureaucratic aggregation, which tends to be slow and expensive. Recent internet-based approaches promise to be real-time and cheap, with few parameters. However, the question of when and how these approaches work remains open. We addressed this question using Wikipedia access logs and category links. Our experiments, replicable and extensible using our open source code and data , test the effect of semantic article filtering, amount of training data, forecast horizon, and model staleness by comparing across 6 diseases and 4 countries using thousands of individual models. We found that our minimal-configuration, language-agnostic article selection process based on semantic relatedness is effective for improving predictions, and that our approach is relatively insensitive to the amount and age of training data. We also found, in contrast to prior work, very little forecasting value, and we argue that this is consistent with theoretical considerations about the nature of forecasting. These mixed results lead us to propose that the currently observational field of internet-based disease surveillance must pivot to include theoretical models of information flow as well as controlled experiments based on simulations of disease.	CI2		

068	Cross-Modal Health State Estimation	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3240508.3241913	Individuals create and consume more diverse data about themselves today than any time in history. Sources of this data include wearable devices, images, social media, geo-spatial information and more. A tremendous opportunity rests within cross-modal data analysis that leverages existing domain knowledge methods to understand and guide human health. Especially in chronic diseases, current medical practice uses a combination of sparse hospital based biological metrics (blood tests, expensive imaging, etc.) to understand the evolving health status of an individual. Future health systems must integrate data created at the individual level to better understand health status perpetually, especially in a cybernetic framework. In this work we fuse multiple user created and open source data streams along with established biomedical domain knowledge to give two types of quantitative state estimates of cardiovascular health. First, we use wearable devices to calculate cardiorespiratory fitness (CRF), a known quantitative leading predictor of heart disease which is not routinely collected in clinical settings. Second, we estimate inherent genetic traits, living environmental risks, circadian rhythm, and biological metrics from a diverse dataset. Our experimental results on 24 subjects demonstrate how multi-modal data can provide personalized health insight. Understanding the dynamic nature of health status will pave the way for better health based recommendation engines, better clinical decision making and positive lifestyle changes.		CE1	Proposta não é de código-aberto. Utiliza dados abertos na validação.
092	Privacy and security in open and trusted health information systems	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1862795.1862802	The Open and Trusted Health Information Systems (OTHIS) Research Group has formed in response to the health sector's privacy and security requirements for contemporary Health Information Systems (HIS). Due to recent research developments in trusted computing concepts, it is now both timely and desirable to move electronic HIS towards privacy-aware and security-aware applications. We introduce the OTHIS architecture in this paper. This scheme proposes a feasible and sustainable solution to meeting real-world application security demands using commercial off-the-shelf systems and commodity hardware and software products.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema
117	Remote Monitoring Applying IoT to Improve Control of Medication Adherence in Geriatric Patients with a complex Treatment Regimen, Lima-Peru	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3429536.3429543	Health care has changed profoundly thanks to the continuous improvement of electronic devices, recent rapid progress in wireless communications and microsystems has allowed the opportunity to automatically collect reliable patient data, yet communication about medication management through Transitions of care can be challenging, when older patients are treated for multiple health conditions in a nursing home. In this document, we propose an innovative architecture that employs Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) technologies with the NodeMCU which is an open source IoT (internet of things) platform and the Raspberry pi 3B+ that is used as an Mqtt server, for a smart pill dispenser, which will promote medication adherence, improve patient / user self-management; also assist in the efficient administration of therapies by reminding and registering medications for patients with a complex treatment regimen.	CI1		
144	DORIC: An Architecture for Data-intensive Real-time Applications	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3229345.3229416	This study presents Doric, a software architecture for data-intensive real-time applications. Dimensions of data-intensive real-time applications are introduced, as well as technologies that enable the implementation of such dimensions. A case study involving a portable electroencephalogram (EEG) enabled data collection based on realistic scenarios found in data-intensive real-time applications. The Doric architecture was implemented using recent technologies (e.g., Apache Kafka) for building real-time data pipelines and streaming applications. This prototype was evaluated in five		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso do código-aberto

			scenarios containing different volumes of data. The obtained results were encouraging and show the potential for applying Doric as a structure to foster the development of modern information systems in organizations and to support serve as a guideline for new corporate architectures.			
155	Annotating with light for remote guidance	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/1324892.1324911	This paper presents a system that will support a remote guidance collaboration, in which a local expert guides a remotely located assistant to perform physical, three-dimensional tasks. The system supports this remote guidance by allowing the expert to annotate, point at and draw upon objects in the remote location using a pen and tablet-based interface to control a laser projection device. The specific design criteria for this system are drawn from a tele-health scenario involving remote medical examination of patients and the paper presents the software architecture and implementation details of the associated hardware. In particular, the algorithm for aligning the representation of the laser projection over the video display of the remote scene is described. Early evaluations by medical specialists are presented, the usability of the system in laboratory experiments is discussed and ideas for future developments are outlined.		CE1	Não deixa explícito o uso de código-aberto
164	Open and trusted information systems/health informatics access control (OTHIS/HIAC)	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/1862758.1862774	Information and Communications Technologies globally are moving towards Service Oriented Architectures and Web Services. The healthcare environment is rapidly moving to the use of Service Oriented Architecture/Web Services systems interconnected via this global open Internet. Such moves present major challenges where these structures are not based on highly trusted operating systems. This paper argues the need of a radical re-think of access control in the contemporary healthcare environment in light of modern information system structures, legislative and regulatory requirements, and security operation demands in Health Information Systems. This paper proposes the Open and Trusted Health Information Systems (OTHIS), a viable solution including override capability to the provision of appropriate levels of secure access control for the protection of sensitive health data.		CE1	Não apresenta o desenvolvimento de um sistema.
189	Prevention of Medication Loss through a Marketplace and Blockchain	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3376044.3376059	The emergence of a digital marketplace in the world and especially in Brazil around 2012 has innovated the way merchants and consumers use technology to commercialize products and services. Consumers are able to search for products and services from many merchants at once while merchants can reach consumers in many different platforms as well as creating a network of business and relationships between the two. This article demonstrates the results of a platform being developed that uses the concepts of a marketplace to prevent the loss of medications that are close to expiring. The solution was developed using a Java, Typescript and NodeJS platform for the consumers to interact with the marketplace using Hyperledger Fabric Blockchain framework, creating a low-cost and simple platform, preventing fraud and and increasing flexibility, security and transparency.		CE1	